

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF DIELECTRIC-FILLED EPOXY RESINS*

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ABSTRACT

A family of composites based on epoxy resins with mineral fillers, are being developed. These composites will have a range of dielectric constants, high breakdown strength for steep-fronted impulse excitation, and mechanical properties suited to such applications as energy storage, wave transmission, and standoff insulation in pulse power systems. The present work reports on the mechanical properties of composites made with three types of fillers: a barium titanate compound (BaTiO_3 , ATD-50), a forsterite compound (MgSiO_3 , ATD-6) and a Geikielite compound (MgTiO_3 , ATD-16). Dependence of these properties on filler, resin composition, and temperature were determined. A filler content of 40 volume % was used. Tensile and Charpy impact tests were conducted at temperatures up to 120°C . Special precautions were taken to ensure uniform temperature distribution in all the tests. Results show that there is a significant dependence of properties on temperature with a less pronounced dependence on filler type. For example, both the tensile and the flexure moduli and strength increased with filler content and decreased with increasing test temperature, whereas the ductility of the composites has the exact opposite dependence. These results will be interpreted in terms of the role of filler.

INTRODUCTION

Pulse power systems involve structural dielectric materials that perform a variety of electrical functions, including voltage standoff, energy storage, transmission of electromagnetic waves, and switching. Frequently, such systems must be designed and fabricated to meet a combination of electrical, thermal, mechanical, chemical and radiational stresses during their lifetime. Many minerals have good dielectric behavior, but are very difficult to fabricate into desired configurations. The techniques of ceramics combine most of the virtues of minerals with the ability to cast complex configurations. However, thick ceramics are difficult to fabricate. The present study is concerned with another class of dielectric materials, thermosetting plastics with powdered mineral fillers, which can be cast with relative ease into large configurations to yield high quality insulating materials over an operating temperature range from about -50°C to $+150^\circ\text{C}$. Such materials are extensively used in structural applications at 50/60 Hz in commercial power systems and also in other applications. Pulse power systems tend to be operated for very short periods at very high levels of electrical stress. Desired mechanical properties will depend upon the application, with some applications requiring more ductility and fracture toughness than others. Impulse behavior involves behavior over a broad

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frequency range, depending upon risetime and duration. Low dielectric loss is required over this range. This paper reports the tensile properties of these composites and their dependence on temperature and filler types.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

The EPON 828 epoxy resin from the Shell Chemical Company was used in this study. This resin is largely composed of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA), but small amounts of higher molecular weight polymer are also present. This resin was chosen because of its easy handling, prior use in insulating composites and commercial availability in large quantities. Dielectric constant of particulate-filled composites is controlled primarily by selecting the appropriate filler materials. Three filler materials (with different dielectric constants were purchased from the Ampex Corporation and were labeled as ATD-6 (k=6, a MgSiO_3 compound), ATD-16 (k=16, a MgTiO_3 compound) and ATD-50 (k=50, a sintered 80% BaTiO_3 , 20% TiO_3 compound). A filler concentration of 40 volume percent was used in all the materials tested in this study.

All filler materials were dried overnight in a vacuum oven at 110°C prior to processing. The raw epoxy materials were devolatilized in a vacuum oven at 80°C for 15 minutes. Calculated amounts of properly dried filler were mechanically mixed with the epoxy resin and hardener at 80°C until a homogeneous mixture was obtained. This mixture was degassed in a vacuum oven until frothing stopped. A small amount, 0.5 phr (parts per hundred parts of resin), of accelerator BDMA was then added to each mixture and hand mixed for 5 minutes before pouring into the appropriate moulds. In this study, the accelerator type and concentration were not varied. The casting composites were degassed, initially cured at 121°C for 2 hours, then finally cured at 204°C for another 2 hours before slow cooling to room temperature. These processing conditions were determined using a combination of torque rheometry and differential scanning calorimetry¹.

The specimens for tensile testing were cast into special molds. These molds were machined from aluminum and coated with a special layer of teflon to facilitate ease of removal. The specimens were 0.25" thick with a gauge length of 2" and a gauge width of 0.5" (conformed to ASTM D638 testing standards). Tensile tests were conducted in materials containing no filler (reference) and 40 volume percent of ATD-6, ATD-16 or ATD-50. A special heater was designed and fabricated that would facilitate tensile testings at temperatures up to 150°C. This heating unit was based on the direct contact heating instead of the more traditional convection heating. This was found necessary to ensure uniformity in temperature across the specimens. Tensile tests were carried out using an Instron machine at 23, 60, 90 and 120°C using this heater for all four types and specimens. A constant crosshead speed of 0.02"/min which corresponded to a constant strain rate of 1.7×10^{-4} /s was used in all the tests.

An instrumented impact tester (GRC 730-I, Dynatup Corporation) was used to determine the impact strength of the cast materials. A charpy test specimen supported at both ends was struck with a falling tup with the notch facing down. The load characteristics on the falling tup during the impact process was recorded. Impact tests were conducted from room temperature to 120°C. After equilibrium has been attained, the test was performed. For the high temperature tests, the specimens were brought to temperature in a separate furnace. Then they were quickly transferred to the testing apparatus. Calibration data show that the specimen transfer only leads to a temperature drop of less than 5°C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 1a to 1d show the tensile behavior of the composites tested under different conditions. The variations of modulus and strength with test temperature are shown in figures 2 and 3 respectively. In each set of test

conditions, five specimens were examined. The data represented in the above figures are from individual specimens. However, it was found that the modified test configurations results in very small scattering. From these tensile data, it was found that the composites filled with ATD-6 and ATD-16 (to 40 volume percent) behaved similar to each other at all four temperatures investigated. The materials softened as test temperature increased as expected, that is the ductility increased with a corresponding drop in strength and modulus. The ductile to brittle transition was found to occur between 90 and 120°C. A more precise determination of this transition is underway. By examining the fracture length of the composites, the deformation at room temperature and 60°C was completely elastic in nature whereas at 90°C, it became elastic-plastic. At 120°C, the ductility of this materials was in excess of 15% and was completely plastic. The materials filled with the ATD-50 powder also exhibited a ductile-to-brittle transition at temperature between 90 and 120°C. The moduli of the ATD-50 filled materials were lower than the ATD-6 and ATD-16 materials at all four temperatures investigated. It appears that the presence of filler enhances the modulus of the materials but decreases their ductility. These findings are indicative of the reinforcing nature of the fillers, and their presence introduces low energy fracture path through the composites. This is in agreement with the experimental observations and theoretical analyses reported in the literature²⁻⁹. Furthermore, the effects of ATD-6 and ATD-16 are very similar and this can be attributed to the chemical nature of these powders. This implies that the effects of such powder additions are more than physical in nature and there are chemical reactions between the epoxy and the powder that can lead to observable mechanical property modifications. The chemical effects of the ATD-6 and ATD-16 powder were investigated using DSC measurements. Results from the thermal study were in accord with this study. Figures 4a and 4b show the fracture surface of the materials with 40% ATD-6 tested at 23°C and 120°C respectively, as revealed by the SEM. The difference in morphology reflects the increase in ductility with test temperature. However, both types of specimens fail by crack initiation at a single point at the surface suggesting that failure occurs at surface imperfection introduced during fabrication^{8,10}.

Summary of the impact tests on these cast composites is given in Table 1. At the two lower temperatures of 23 and 60°C, the amount of energy that the materials can absorb prior to failure is quite independent of the presence of filler powder. In addition, there appears to be little temperature dependence of impact behavior between these two temperature. The maximum load and the energy dissipated at this maximum load also exhibit the same behavior (independence of filler and temperature). However, at 120°C there is a near ten-fold increase in the energy absorption capability of the pure system compared to the lower temperature data (total energies absorbed at 23, 60 and 120°C in this system are 0.3, 0.3 and 2.06 J respectively). This is accompanied by a corresponding increase in the energy at maximum load while the maximum load remains unchanged. This means that the increase in the total energy absorption and the energy at maximum load arise from an increase in the ductility and not the strength. Comparing this impact information with the corresponding tensile data from the same pure material review that the strength of the pure sample decreases with increasing temperature as expected. However, the elongation to failure (ductility) of the 120°C sample is actually lower than that of the 90°C sample. We believe that the low ductility observed in the tensile test of the 120°C sample is real since all five samples exhibited the same behavior. This decrease in ductility (in tensile testing) and decrease in strength with temperature from 90 to 120°C is a direct result of the onset of glass transition. The impact data also exhibit a disrupt change at temperature between 60 and 120°C. This change is most likely also a consequence of the glass transition. However, the measure energy absorption capability of this pure system increases at 120°C contrary to the decrease in strength and ductility in the tensile test. This means that the glass transition has

Figure 1. Tensile stress-strain behavior for (a) unfilled materials, (b) with 40% ATD-6, (c) with 40% ATD-16 and (d) with 40% ATD-50.

Figure 2. Dependence of the elastic modulus on temperature for different materials.

Figure 3. Dependence of strength on temperature for different materials.

50 microns

Figure 4. Scanning electron micrographs showing the fracture morphology for the materials with 40% ATD-6 powder tensile tested at (a) room temperature and (b) 120°C.

difference influence on different tests. In the tensile mode, the soft flexible chains at high temperatures are not capable of sustaining tensile stress whereas the same soft chains are more efficient in transmitting the phonon waves generated by the high strain rate impact tests resulting in a dramatic increase in energy absorption. As for the filled samples, no dramatic change in either the impact or the tensile data at 120°C. This is indicative of the increase in the glass transition temperature due to the presence of the filler.

Table 1 Summary of Impact Data

Temp (°C)	Specimens	Max Load (kN)	Energy at Max Load (J)	Total Energy (J)
23	Pure	0.44	0.18	0.31
	ATD-6	0.51	0.15	0.33
	ATD-16	0.52	0.14	0.23
	ATD-50	0.45	0.11	0.22
60	Pure	0.47	0.20	0.29
	ATD-6	0.68	0.23	0.41
	ATD-16	0.60	0.20	0.36
	ATD-50	0.68	0.27	0.38
120	Pure	0.41	0.82	2.06
	ATD-6	0.64	0.28	0.49
	ATD-16	0.66	0.23	0.43
	ATD-50	0.88	0.26	0.52

Details of the electrical properties of these composites will be presented in a separate paper. However, it is appropriate to include some typical dielectric data here. It was found that within the range of frequency examined (from 1 kHz to 100 kHz), the dielectric constants in these materials are independent of frequency. On the contrary, the dissipation factor was found to increase with increasing frequency. For example, the dissipation factor for 828/NMA/BDMA/ATD50 is 0.65×10^{-2} at 1 kHz and this factor increases to 1.3×10^{-2} at 100 kHz. The observed dielectric constants are less than the prorated values of an ideal mixture of ceramic and epoxy. Nevertheless, the presence of dielectric filler does enhance the dielectric constant. This dependence permits the control of dielectric constant by varying either the filler content and/or the filler type.

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